

FOREIGN OBJECT INDUCED FIBER UNDULATION INFLUENCE ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE

H. Herranen^{1*}, M. Eerme¹, H. Lend¹, A. Kuusik², S. Czichon³, J. Kers⁴, M. Piirlaid⁵

¹Department of Machinery, Tallinn University of Technology, Tallinn, Estonia

²ELIKO Competence Center, Tallinn, Estonia,

³Elan-Ausy GmbH, Hamburg,

⁴Department of Materials Engineering, Tallinn University of Technology, Tallinn, Estonia,

⁵Department of Polymer Materials, Tallinn Univ. of Technology, Tallinn Estonia

* Corresponding author (henrik.herranen@ttu.ee)

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1 General Introduction

Composite materials have found a wide range of applications in engineering due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, resistance to fatigue and environmental influences. Fiber composites are laminated anisotropic materials, which damage is often not easily detectable. The increasing demand for structural health monitoring has stimulated efforts to integrate self-sensing capabilities into materials and structures. Surface mounted sensors are susceptible to damage and their protection from environment is often noticeable extra weight gain. Embedding the sensors in housing allows for protection from adverse environmental conditions. It is also the only means suitable for creating an autonomous structure with a smooth surface finish. Previous efforts to integrate sensors and MEMS devices into fiber-reinforced composites have often required that such a device be placed between the fiber layers of a composite as it is being fabricated. As a result, the device is usually surrounded by the matrix phase, typically a polymer, which is generally the weaker phase within the composite. Interlaminar stresses arise at or near the inclusions and could result in delamination, which in turn reduces load carrying capability and further reduces the ability of an embedded sensor to detect its surrounding environment. Therefore, it is necessary to characterize the effects of embedding sensors on the mechanical properties of the host structural composite material.

The main sources of problems are caused by elastic properties mismatch, specifically high difference of the modulus of elasticity.

Embedding electronics inside mechanically working composite creates a controversy. The metallic and semiconductor parts with high stiffness do not comply with the strains of operating composite and composite materials on the other hand do not match with the embedded foreign objects, which generate severe stress concentrations in the host structure.

Selective laser sintering (SLS) is technology, which allows layer-wise build-up of very complex geometrical shapes. It is an additive layer technology (ALT). SLS is technology which is feasible solution for manufacturing a enclosure around electronics, which are to be integrated inside the main material.

This article is focused on embedding SLS produced components inside main structure. SLS built enclosure around composite reduces the elasticity mismatch or even isolates the un-compatible materials from each other.

Inserting foreign object inside the laminate is similar to the effect of void on the composite structure. The change of geometry causes fiber undulation around the object and locally increased waviness. This change affects significantly structural performance of the composite [1]. Beside the undulation the embedded object has different elasticity – if it is electronics, then it is much stiffer and causes extra stresses. In this article SLS produced PA-12 nylon enclosure for electronics is inserted in the host material. The mechanical properties of PA-12 nylon are very similar to polyester resins and epoxy resins. Additionally SLS produced PA-12 nylon could weaken by hygrothermal influences [2]. A phenomenon called plasticization occurs. This

further reduces the mechanical strength of the two material interface. In order to simulate that, the foreign objects had no friction enhancing or room interlocking features to increase contact zone rigidness.

2 Methodology

Embedding the electronic components directly in composite may lead to impairments of the components during fabrication or exploitation of the composite structure (mechanical defects, overheating, etc). For that reason the additive layer technology has been employed for manufacturing housings which can host the electronic components. Any embedded components have impact on mechanical, thermal, etc properties of the composite structure. Thus, the design of housings is necessary. First the design of experiment has been performed. Next the specimens with ALT manufactured embedded structures are fabricated and mechanical tests performed.

The finite element (FE) model has been developed for modeling the stress-strain behavior of the composite structure with embedded components. The finite element model is validated through comparison with digital image correlation scanner results. Also, the results obtained from mechanical tests and FE model are compared. The FE model developed covers fiber undulation caused by embedded objects.

Based the experimental results the mathematical model is developed.

Finally the size and shape optimization of the embedded structure has been performed. The size of the pockets formed at ends of the embedded structure and the mechanical stresses around the embedded structure are considered as objective functions. The multicriteria optimization problem posed has been divided into multistage optimization procedure and solved by use of weighted summation technique. Due to presence of integer variables the genetic algorithm (GA) was employed.

3 Specimen design

It is correct to point out that in current context the design of specimen contains mainly design of housing for electronics which will be mounted in specimen (in addition to specimen dimensions, the shape and dimensions of the housing are considered as design variables).

The strength characteristics of the specimen have been analyzed. The following optimality criteria were selected

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= H(x_1, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow \min, \\ F_2 &= L(x_1, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow \min, \\ F_3 &= \alpha_{max}(x_1, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow \min, \\ F_4 &= \sigma_f(x_1, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow \max, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where H, L, α_{max} and σ_f stand for the height and length of the pocket, maximal angle of the pocket diagonal side and failure stress, respectively. Parameters x_1, \dots, x_n stand for design variables.

Before selection of multicriteria optimization strategy it is important to understand general characteristic behaviour of the optimality criteria used [3,4,5]. Preliminary analysis of the optimality criteria (1) allows to conclude, that in general:

- The optimality criteria F_1, F_2, F_3 given by (1) are not contradictional (decrease or increase for the same dataset).
- The optimality criterion F_4 increase with decreasing values of criteria F_1, F_2, F_3 and vice versa. However, criterion F_4 is subjected to maximization, and there is not contradictional with criteria F_1, F_2, F_3 .

Thus, there is no need for applying Pareto optimality concept for handling conflicting objectives. In the following the weighted summation technique is employed. The objectives (1) should be first normalized, due to their different magnitude. The normalization is performed by formulas

$$f_i(\bar{x}) = \frac{F_i(\bar{x}) - \min F_i(\bar{x})}{\max F_i(\bar{x}) - \min F_i(\bar{x})}, \quad (2)$$

for objectives subjected to minimization (F_1, F_2, F_3) and by formulas

$$f_4(\bar{x}) = \frac{\max F_4(\bar{x}) - F_4(\bar{x})}{\max F_4(\bar{x}) - \min F_4(\bar{x})}, \quad (3)$$

for objectives subjected to maximization (F_4).

In (2)-(3) $i = 1, 2, 3$ and \bar{x} stands for the vector of design variables.

According to weighted summation technique the combined objective can be written as

$$f = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i f_i \rightarrow \min, \quad (4)$$

where w_i stand for the weights of the objectives (2)-(3) and are evaluated as

$$w_1 = w_2 = w_3 = w_4 = 0.25, \quad (5)$$

i.e. all are considered to have the same importance. The housings for embedded electronics with different shapes have different number of design parameters x_1, \dots, x_n . For that reason the two level optimization strategy has been introduced [6,7,8].

3.1. Higher level design

In higher level design stage the most suitable shape and size of the housing have been determined. The following geometrical shapes were considered:

- rectangular
- trapezoid
- round
- ellipse

The size of the each shape has been varied. Two parameters have been considered for each shape with the exception of trapezoid and circle. Circular cross-section has only diameter as variable and trapezoid has three parameters: height, width and the angle of sides relative to base. The full factorial design of experiment has been employed for shapes except trapezoid. In latter case the Taguchi design of experiment was applied. The size range was chosen to accommodate the structure to specific electronic device. Circular cross-section has no real application potential. It was used in order to investigate the fiber undulation around short object. The variables are discrete values as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Variables of geometrical shapes

Shape	Length [mm]	Height [mm]	Side angle [°]
Ellipse	10; 25; 40;	1; 2; 3;	-
Circular	diameter 1.5mm; 2mm; 4mm;		
Rectangular	10; 25; 40;	1; 2; 3;	-
Trapezious	10; 25; 40;	1; 2; 3;	50; 53; 56;

The level values for Taguchi method is therefore 3. Three parameters and three levels would require in

full factorial testing 3^3 or 27 combinations. Taguchi design matrix is depicted in Table 2. P1, P2 and P3 are parameters. Based on that methodology the trapezoid shape dimensions are derived as shown in Table 3.

Table 2 Parameter values and experiment

Experiment	P1	P2	P3
1	1	1	1
2	1	2	2
3	1	3	3
4	2	1	2
5	2	2	3
6	2	3	1
7	3	1	3
8	3	2	1
9	3	3	2

Table 3 Parameter values for trapezoid

Nr.	Width, mm	Height, mm	Angle, °
1	10	1	50
2	10	2	53
3	10	3	56
4	25	1	53
5	25	2	56
6	25	3	50
7	40	1	56
8	40	2	50
9	40	3	53

In the case of full factorial design, three parameters and three levels are needed $3^3 = 27$ testing combinations instead of 9 used for Taguchi design. Numerical analysis performed allows concluding that the ellipse appears to be most suitable shape of the housing. Also the optimal values of the height and width of the housing are found to converge to 1 and 25, respectively. However, the results depend on selected values of weights (5), also from accuracy of the measured values of objectives functions. The smaller height of the housing is obviously better – causing less damage of the structure by not influencing the straightness of fiber bundles. Actually here are a lot of options for the selection,

design of embedded electronics depending on its price, aptitude, etc. Unfortunately, not all variants of embedded electronics can be fitted in housing with height values equal to 1mm and even to 2 mm. Thus, different heights should be considered for future analysis (cost can be included).

3.2. Lower level design

In lower level design the selected elliptic shape of the housing is assumed, but certain improvement of the shape is introduced. Namely, the elliptic shape is divided into two parts, consisting from two ellipses with different half-axis (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Design variables: minor half-axes

The minor half-axes of the ellipse are considered as design variables. For fixed values of the minor half-axes the major half-axes values are determined by total length of the ellipse and continuity conditions. The remaining design variable considered in lower level design is the length of the specimen.

Preliminary numerical results obtained include optimal design where the value of the length of specimen is near minimal value considered and the minor half-axes of the lower ellipse (see Figure 1) is substantially smaller than minor half-axes of the upper ellipse (1/2...1/4 depending on total height of the ellipse).

The mathematical model introduced for data fitting is based on use of artificial neural networks and is satisfactory. However, in order to improve the accuracy of the obtained results, the dataset used need to be completed, the design area enlarged (limits of design variables extended).

4 Experimental testing

4.1 Specimen manufacturing

The reinforcement is biaxial $0^\circ/90^\circ$ non-crimp type glass fiber fabric type Saint-Gobain ELT 600 125 FMA 5008 C with surface density 600g/m^2 . The matrix is vinylester resin ATLAC 580 ACT with hardener Butanox M50 (1,5% volume fraction of resin). The mechanical properties of the laminate are depicted in Table 4.

The foreign objects are manufactured with selective laser sintering machine EOS GmbH Formiga P100. Selective laser sintering technology allows to create complex shapes with almost no geometrical limits. The base material is PA-12 polymer (EOS PA2200). The foreign objects were cleaned with pressurized air and acetone before the lamination process to remove any residue from laser sintering process.

The foreign objects were laminated between 6 plies of laminate on the mid-plane, the lay-up notation is $[0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/\text{ForeignObject}/0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ]$. The specimen was laminated at 0.8 bar vacuum and post-cured after manufacturing at 60°C for 16 hours.

The specimens were cut-out from workpiece with high speed milling machine at 32000 RPM with low feed rate in order to minimize the specimen edge delamination probability.

Figure 2 Resin pocket example

E_x, E_y	19,6GPa
E_z	5GPa
ν_{xy}	0,26
ν_{yz}	0,01
ν_{xz}	0,01
G_{xy}	3,28GPa
G_{xz}, G_{yz}	1,6GPa
σ_x^c, σ_y^c	215,9MPa
σ_x^t, σ_y^t	304,7MPa
$\tau_{xy}^{0,2}$	23,1MPa

Table 4 Mechanical properties of laminate

4.2 Examination of preliminary specimens

The undulation size and shape will be estimated from sectioned specimens with microphotography. The measurable parameters are depicted in Figure 2. It is known from various authors that fiber waviness is one of the most critical parameters of composite mechanical properties[11,12,]. In this article simple waviness parameters like amplitude and wavelength are not sufficient to describe the resin pocket properties. This is because the resin pocket around foreign object is single event not repeating pattern. Lemanski and Sutcliffe [10] measured fiber misalignment angle influence on the mechanical properties of unidirectional laminate. In this research the measurable parameters are as mentioned in methodology section the height H and length L of the pocket, maximal angle α_{max} and average angle α_{avg} of the pocket diagonal side and failure stress σ_f , respectively. All the parameters except of failure stress can be measured from microcope pictures. The examination results are shown for all three thicknesses accordingly in Table 5, Table 6 and Table 7.

The data from these tables was inserted in weighted summation optimization procedure. The weight values are taken from equation (5).

Table 5 measured parameters for 1 mm thick foreign objects. 1-ellipse, 2-rectangular, 3-trapezoid.

Shape	Length [mm]	Pocket height [μ m]	Pocket length [μ m]	Avg. undulation angle ($^\circ$)	Max. Undulation angle ($^\circ$)
1	10	689	5204	7	10,2
1	10	546	3169	9,3	10,6
1	25	648	8820	4	7,8
1	40	642	10790	3,6	8,4
1	40	995	11669	5,4	12
2	10	1184	9451	5	6,9
2	10	1257	10480	4,6	8,4
2	25	1077	11087	3,2	7
2	25	1256	11662	2	5
2	40	1248	13984	3	3,8
3	10	926	7119	8	10,7
3	25	986	9473	5,4	10,5
3	25	1063	9444	6,2	13,5
3	4	1057	7264	6,7	8,5

Table 6 Results for 2mm thick foreign objects

Shape	Length [mm]	Pocket height [μ m]	Pocket length [μ m]	Avg. undulation angle ($^\circ$)	Max. Undulation angle ($^\circ$)
1	1	1520	10280	4	7,3
1	1	1747	9984	3,3	5,7
1	2,5	1027	9036	4,6	6
1	4	1846	13830	6,4	9,8
2	1	2232	9976	9,8	17,7
2	1	2097	11546	9	14,5
2	2,5	2195	12760	9,6	16
2	4	2241	10582	7,8	12,1
3	1	1822	13736	6,8	10,1
3	2,5	1779	10533	8,3	14,6
3	4	1576	11467	9	16,6

Table 7 Results for 3mm thick foreign objects

Shape	Length [mm]	Pocket height [μm]	Pocket length [μm]	Avg. undulation angle (°)	Max. undulation angle (°)
1	1	2501	16746	5,2	8,6
1	1	2262	15335	6,7	10
1	2,5	951	8417	11,3	19,1
1	2,5	1301	8018	12,6	21
1	4	1544	18560	4	8,4
2	1	3151	13220	10	13,3
2	1	3420	13732	7,4	12,2
2	2,5	3000	11494	11	20
2	4	3069	11573	10,4	13,8
3	1	2483	13116	12,5	17,3
3	2,5	1722	8843	17	29
3	2,5	1596	6417	19	31
3	4	2643	13908	8,4	11

4.3 Design of new specimens

Based on the results of weighted summation optimization method the smallest influence on fiber undulation has ellipse with dimensions 25mm x 2mm. It was discovered during the microscopic examination procedure that some slender ellipses tried to conform to the flat manufacturing mould surface by bending the closer surface curvature to collinearity with mould surface. Therefore it is proposed that most suitable shape for foreign object should be instead composed of two half ellipses with different minor radiuses. Batch with different half ellipse combinations was manufactured. The length of ellipse stood the same 25mm value, but the minor radius combinations were varied as depicted in

Table 8. Two possible thicknesses for the whole foreign object were chosen. Also an un-common combination of half-ellipse and straight line was used(the sharp ends were rounded by fillet with radius 0,18mm).

Table 8 Dimensions of new specimens

Length [mm]	Minor radius 1, [mm]	Minor radius 2 [mm]	Total thickness [mm]
25	2,75	0,25	3
25	1,5	0,5	2
25	3	flat	3
25	1,75	0,25	2
25	1,25	0,75	2
25	2,5	0,5	3

4.4 Examination of new specimens

The new batch specimen had microphotography based measurements repeated analogically to the previous batch. The results are in Table 9.

Table 9 Results for new specimens

Shape	Pocket length [μm]	Pocket height [μm]	Avg. undulation angle (°)	Max. undulation angle (°)
1	4117	806	8,3	12,8
2	9203	1827	10,8	15
3	3650	764	8,8	12
4	14543	1653	5,5	11,3
5	1773	664	16,6	24
6	5705	1154	9,9	14,5

4.5 Mechanical testing

The specimens with embedded object were tested only for tensile loading. It was concluded from previous research [9] that the main source of failure is delamination initiated from resin pockets at the interface surface of foreign object and matrix. The failure mechanisms are similar for compression and tension, only difference is the properties reduction magnitude. The tensile testing is less sensitive to manufacturing faults, therefore it was chosen as more reliable method. Testing was carried out with tensile testing machine Instron 8516 coupled with digital image correlation (DIC) scanner GOM ARAMIS 2M. The base standard for test settings was ISO 527-4(equivalent to ASTM D3039). The

testing results are depicted on Figure 3 and summarized in Table 10.

Figure 3 Tensile testing results chart

No.	Thickness of undist. section [mm]	Thickest point at for.object [mm]	Minor radius 1 [mm]	Minor radius 2 [mm]	Failure stress [MPa]
SLS1	3,12	6,4	2,75	0,25	155,6
SLS2	2,93	5,3	1,5	0,5	231,6
SLS3	3,1	6,6	3	0	236,1
SLS4	3	5,3	1,75	0,25	202,8
SLS5	3	5,1	1,25	0,75	261,2
SLS6	3	6,3	2,5	0,5	252,3
Average:					223,28

Table 10 Tensile testing results

The highest strength had specimen number 5, which was 16,9% higher than the average. This specimen had also very small resin pocket which was tightly packet by three 90° fiber yarns. Cross-section image is shown in Figure 4. The tensile strength was determined from DIC scanning images. The laminate was considered to failed after the first macrocrack occurrence.

Figure 4 Specimen number 5 cross-section image. Foreign object visible at the right side of the picture.

4.6 Digital image correlation results

The strain distribution around and inside the embedded device was measured in thickness direction at the side of the specimen using digital image correlation scanner GOM ARAMIS 2M similarly to one of the authors previous works [9]. The surface strains of the specimens were measured with a digital image correlation system (DIC) GOM ARAMIS 2M. The measuring volume was set to 35 mm x 25 mm. System measuring parameters were as follows: the computational size was set to 3, validity quote to 55%. The computation type was set to total strain method and plane stress.

Figure 5 The strain distribution of specimen 5 at failure stress

The major strain distribution around on the specimen edge is shown in Figure 5. It is evident that the delamination starts from the resin pocket, although it is quite small.

5 Conclusions

The two level optimization procedure is developed for solving multicriteria optimization problem posed. An analysis of the optimality criteria is performed and the weighted summation technique applied. The response modeling is utilized by use of artificial neural networks. The multilevel optimization strategy proposed allows decomposing initial problem into two simpler tasks, which can be solved sequentially. The obtained numerical results contain optimal shape and size of the housing for embedded electronics. The optimization procedure helps to minimize the resin pocket dimensions, which criticality as a delamination starting point has been verified by the digital image correlation scanning.

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